

Synthesis and Characterisation of some 1-Aminomethyl-3-substituted-4-(5-nitro-2-thienylidene)amino-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiones

BALAKRISHNA KALLURAYA* and ALPHONSUS D'SOUZA

Department of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 17 July 1993, revised 30 August 1993, accepted 19 October 1993

4-Amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles are the starting materials for the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic derivatives, which are of great importance in medicinal chemistry¹. The Mannich bases possess various biological activities².

Keeping in view of these observations and in continuation of our work³ on the synthesis of biologically active nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocycles, we report here the synthesis of 3-substituted-4-(5-nitro-2-thienylidene)amino-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiones (2) and their Mannich bases (3-9).

The triazoles carrying alkyl, aryl and aryloxy methyl substituents at 3-position were prepared as per the reported procedures⁴ (Scheme 1). 5-Nitrothiophene-2-aldehydediacetate was obtained by the formylation⁵ of thiophene followed by nitration⁶. The triazoles (1) when condensed with 5-nitrothiophene-2-aldehydediacetate in alcohol medium using concentrated sulphuric acid as the catalyst, gave the Schiff bases (2) in good yields (Table 1). The latter (2) when treated with formaldehyde and the appropriate amine in ethanol gave the Mannich bases (3-9) in moderate to good yields (Table 2).

The ¹H nmr spectrum of Schiff base 2c showed a triplet at δ 1.2 and a quartet at δ 2.65 integrating for three and two protons of the ethyl group. The nitrothiophene β -protons showed two doublets at δ 7.45 (*J* 4.5 Hz) and 7.75 (*J* 4.5 Hz)

integrating for one proton each. The $-N=CH-$ signal appeared at δ 10.45 integrating for one proton. The signal due to SH proton, however, was not observed, presumably due to the facile thiol-thione tautomerism of 5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles. The nmr spectra of a few other Schiff

Scheme 1

bases were also recorded and conformed with the assigned structure. The mass spectrum of **2g** showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 365, consistent with the molecular formula $C_{13}H_8ClN_5S_2O_2$.

In the nmr spectrum of Mannich base **3a**, the methyl proton appeared as a singlet at δ 2.2 integrating for three protons. The CH_2 protons of morpholine adjacent to nitrogen resonated as a triplet at δ 2.55, while the CH_2 protons adjacent to oxygen resonated as a triplet at δ 3.45, each integrating for four protons. The signals due to $-NCH_2$ proton appeared as a singlet at δ 4.8 integrating for two protons. The β -protons of the nitrothiophene appeared as two doublets at δ 7.55 (J 4.5 Hz) and 7.8 (J 4.5 Hz), each integrating for one proton each. The signal due to $-N=CH-$ proton appeared at δ 10.4, integrating for one proton. The chemical shift values for **3d** and **8b** are as follows : **3d** δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.22 (2H, d, $-NCH_2$), 6.55–6.85 (5H, m, ArH and NH), 7.52 (1H, d, thiophene 3-H), 7.76 (1H, d, thiophene 4-H), 10.37 (1H, s, $N=CH$); **8b** δ 1.4 (6H, s, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.5 (4H, s, CH_2-N-CH_2), 4.8 (2H, s, $-NCH_2$), 5.0 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.52–6.8 (m, ArH), 7.51 (1H, d, thiophene

3-H), 7.75 (1H, d, thiophene 4-H), δ 10.3 (1H, s, $N=CH$). The mass spectrum of Mannich bases showed the characteristic molecular ion peaks. The m/z and relative abundance of molecular ions and fragment ions of some typical compounds are given in Scheme 2.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, nmr spectrum on an EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D300 spectrometer (70 eV).

4-(5-Nitro-2-thienylidene)amino-5-mercapto-3-substituted-1,2,4-triazoles (2a-p). *General procedure* : An equimolecular mixture of the triazole (**1**; 0.02 mol) and 5-nitrothiophene-2-aldehydediacetate (0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed with concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.5 ml) for 1–2 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, the solid product separated was crystallised from a suitable solvent. The physical data of the compounds (yields 50–81%) are given in Table 1.

- a) $R = C_3H_7$, $R' =$ Morpholino
 b) $R = p$ -Cresyloxymethyl, $R' =$ Piperidino
 c) $R = p$ -Chlorophenyl, $R' =$ Morpholino

Scheme 2

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **2^a**

Compd no.	R	M p.(°C) ^a / (Colour)
2a	H	246–48 ^a (Yellow)
b	Methyl	255–57 ^a (Yellow)
c	Ethyl	201–02 ^a (Yellow)
d	Propyl	181–82 ^a (Yellow)
e	Phenyl	210–11 ^b (Red)
f	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	216–18 ^b (Orange-red)
g	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	244–45 ^b (Orange-red)
h	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	204–05 ^b (Orange)

NOTE

Table-1 (Contd.)

Table-2 (Contd.)

i	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	213–14 ^b (Red)
j	Benzyl	208–09 ^b (Yellow)
k	Phenoxy-methyl	184–85 ^a (Orange)
l	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxy-methyl	160–62 ^a (Yellow)
m	<i>p</i> -Tolyloxymethyl	173–74 ^a (Yellow)
n	<i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>m</i> -cresyloxymethyl	183–84 ^a (Yellow)
o	2,4-Dichloro-phenoxy-methyl	260–62 ^b (Yellow)
p	α -Naphthoxy-methyl	175–77 ^b (Brown)

*Solvent for crystallisation : ^aethanol; ^bacetic acid.

1-Aminomethyl-3-substituted-4-(5-nitro-2-thienylidene)amino-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiones (3–9). *General procedure* : A solution of the appropriate Schiff base (**2**; 0.01 mol), formaldehyde (40%, 1.5 ml) and the amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was stirred for 1–2 h, and then left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was crystallised from a suitable solvent to yield the product. The physical data of the compounds **3–9** (yields 44–90%) are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3–9***

Compd. no.	R	NR ¹ R ²	M.p.(°C) / (Colour)
3a	Methyl	Morpholino	165–66 ^a (Yellow)
b	Methyl	Piperidino	159–60 ^a (Yellow)
c	Methyl	Diphenylamino	184–85 ^a (Yellow)
d	Methyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	84–5 ^a (Orange)
4a	Ethyl	Morpholino	140–42 ^a (Yellow)
b	Ethyl	Piperidino	150–52 ^a (Yellow)
c	Ethyl	Diphenylamino	150–51 ^a (Orange-red)
d	Ethyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	117–18 ^a (Yellow)
5a	Propyl	Morpholino	124–25 ^a (Yellow)
b	Propyl	Piperidino	109–10 ^a (Yellow)
c	Propyl	Dipenylamino	125–26 ^a (Yellow)
d	Propyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	146–47 ^a (Yellow)
6a	Phenyl	Morpholino	154–56 ^b (Red)
b	Phenyl	Piperidino	147–48 ^b (Red)
c	Phenyl	Diphenylamino	184–85 ^b (Orange)
d	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	118–19 ^b (Orange-red)
7a	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	176–77 ^b (Yellow)
b	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Piperidino	160–62 ^b (Yellow)
c	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Diphenylamino	215–16 ^b (Orange-yellow)
d	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	198–99 ^b (Orange)
8a	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxy-methyl	Morpholino	145–46 ^a (Yellow)
b	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxy-methyl	Piperidino	140–41 ^a (Yellow)
c	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxy-methyl	Dipenylamino	123–24 ^a
d	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxy-methyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	106–07 ^a (Yellow)

Table-2 (Contd.)

9a	<i>p</i> -Cresyloxy methyl	Morpholino	126-27 ^a (Yellow)
b	<i>p</i> -Cresyloxy-methyl	Piperidino	109-10 ^a (Yellow)
c	<i>p</i> -Cresyloxy-methyl	Dipenylamino	104-05 ^a (Yellow)
d	<i>p</i> -Cresyloxy-methyl	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	86-87 ^a (Yellow)

*Solvent for crystallisation : ^aethanol; ^bacetic acid.

References

1. C. TEMPLE in "The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds", ed. J. A. MONTGOMERY, Wiley, New York, 198.
2. B. RICHIERI, "Die Mannich Reaktion", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1959; M. TRAMONTINI, L. ANGIOLINI and N. GHEDINI, *Polymer*, 1988, **29**, 771.
3. B. S. HOLLA, B. KALLURAYA and S. N. SHETTY, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1992, **2**, 61; B. KALLURAYA, S. N. SHETTY and J. K. JOHN, *Chimica Acta Turcica*, 1992, **20**, 173.
4. K. S. DHAKA, J. MOHAN, V. K. CHADHA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 288; K. R. REID and N. D. HEINDEL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 925; B. S. HOLLA and B. KALLURAYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 683.
5. H. D. HARTOUGH, "Thiophene and its Derivatives", Interscience, New York, 1952.
6. P. R. FOURNARI and J. P. CHANE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1963, 479 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **59**, 1570).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. B. S. Holla, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities and Head, R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for analytical and spectral data.